

PSYCHOSOCIAL SUPPORT ACTIVITIES ON LEARNERS' PSYCHOSOCIAL READINESS AND WELL-BEING IN ELEMENTARY EDUCATION

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Psychosocial Support Activities on Learners' Psychosocial Readiness and Well-Being in Elementary Education

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Abstract

This study investigates the relationship between the implementation of Psychosocial Support Activities (PSA) and the psychosocial readiness and well-being of learners participating in in-person classes in the Second Congressional District of Bohol for the 2022-2023 school year. A total of 114 teachers and 114 learners were selected through simple random sampling. Utilizing a descriptive survey design, data were collected via questionnaires to assess PSA implementation levels, learners' psychosocial readiness, and psychosocial well-being. Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient was employed to analyze the relationships among these variables. Results indicated a very high level of PSA implementation, suggesting effective school practices. Furthermore, learners exhibited very high psychosocial readiness, indicating strong psychological, social, and emotional preparedness for the learning environment. While PSA implementation did not significantly influence learners' psychosocial readiness or well-being, a substantial positive correlation was found between the two latter variables. Based on these findings, the study advocates for integrating Basic Psychosocial Support into the School Disaster Risk Reduction and Management (DRRM) Contingency Plan, enabling educators to support students facing distress effectively. This research suggests the importance of psychosocial support in enhancing students' overall educational experiences and well-being institutionalizing psychological interventions and integrating Basic Psychosocial Support into School DRRM Contingency Plans to foster a holistic learning environment to enhance students' capacity.

Keywords: *psychosocial, well being, learners, education, activities*

Introduction

When the pandemic broke out, a massive change in the educational landscape happened. After two years, most schools are back open and in the stage of recovery from the damage to learning caused by the pandemic. The pandemic created an immense disruption of the educational system which affects over 1.5 billion of learners. It has the greatest impact on the learners' quality of learning experience and mental health (Barrot et al., 2021).

As classes have been in full swing, educators must be prepared to respond to the academic, social, and emotional needs of their learners during the opening of classes. Some studies shown significant mental health problems experienced by children because of the prolonged quarantine and substantial learning loss (Noguera, 2021).

Students face new challenges and stressors that arise during the transition period of in-person classes. They take a lot of adjustments to the school environment, learning modality, and additional safety protocols, as well as mix of pleasant and difficult feelings. Thus, DepEd observe the imperative to provide psychosocial support (PSS) to protect the learners' socio-emotional well-being and to develop their coping skills during the transition period (Llego, 2022).

As directed by DepEd Memorandum No. 34, s. 2022, all schools were asked to implement the Psychosocial Support Activities (PSA) during the first week of School Year 2022-2023, beginning on August 22, 2022. Learners were given series of psychosocial support activities to assess how they respond from the given activities and help them adjust during the transition of face-to-face classes. These activities will help the teachers determine which psychosocial concepts their learners need more of their attention.

This study aimed to determine the relationship of the implementation of the Psychosocial Support Activities (PSA) and the learners' psychosocial readiness and well-being in the in-person classes in the Second Congressional District of Bohol for the school year 2022-2023.

Research Questions

Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of implementation in the Psychosocial Support Activities (PSA) program planning and management, attainment of objectives, delivery of program content, participants' learning, provision of support materials; and program preparation?
2. What is the learners' level of psychosocial readiness in psychosocial skills and psychosocial adjustment?
3. What is the learners' level of psychosocial well-being in emotional well-being, social well-being, and resilience?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of implementation and psychosocial readiness, level of implementation and psychosocial well-being, and psychosocial readiness and psychosocial well-being?

Methodology

This research employed a descriptive survey design to evaluate the implementation of Psychosocial Support Activities, assess learners' psychosocial readiness, and determine their well-being. Conducted in selected public elementary schools within the 2nd Congressional District of Bohol, the study focused specifically on Grade 6 teachers and learners due to their maturity in comprehending survey questions.

A sample of 185 participants was derived through Slovin's formula from a total of 344 elementary schools, using simple random sampling. However, only 114 valid responses each from teachers and learners were ultimately retrieved after addressing incomplete questionnaires, resulting in a total of 228 valid responses.

The researcher utilized a Likert-type scale questionnaire, developing separate sets for teachers and learners. These assessed various dimensions of psychosocial support and readiness. Validity was established with input from a licensed psychologist and through pilot testing in a different district, yielding a high reliability index of 0.9. The data collection process involved obtaining necessary approvals from academic and school administration, followed by data tabulation and analysis to interpret the results effectively.

The descriptive survey design was suitable for gathering current information from Grade 6 teachers and learners, who were selected for their maturity in understanding the survey. Simple random sampling ensured representativeness, and the use of Slovin's formula determined a reliable sample size. A Likert-type scale questionnaire effectively measured psychosocial dimensions, and validation through expert input and pilot testing ensured both reliability and accuracy of the data.

Results and Discussion

The data on the implementation of Psychosocial Support Activities (PSA) in schools indicates a very high level of effectiveness. Key areas of success include program content delivery and participants' learning, while program preparation showed a need for improvement. High-rated items included encouraging learner participation and using standardized psychosocial support assessment tools

Table 1. *Level of Implementation in the Psychosocial Support Activities (PSA)*

<i>Program Assessment</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.1. Program Planning and Management	3.35	VHLI
1.1.2. The PSA was managed by the teacher and school head efficiently	3.40	VHLI
1.1.1. The Psychosocial Support Activities (PSA) was delivered as planned	3.33	VHLI
1.1.3. The PSA was well-structured	3.32	VHLI
1.2. Attainment of Objectives	3.36	VHLI
1.2.1. The PSA objectives were clearly presented	3.50	VHLI
1.2.2. The series of activities were logically arranged	3.38	VHLI
1.2.3. The PSA objectives were attained	3.20	HLI
1.3. Delivery of Program Content	3.45	VHLI
2.3.2. Activities were based on standard psychosocial support assessment tool	3.53	VHLI
1.3.1. Activities were appropriate to the learners	3.52	VHLI
1.3.6. Instructions on the activities were clearly presented	3.51	VHLI
1.3.3. Activities were interesting in generating ideas and emotions	3.47	VHLI
1.3.5. The teacher established rapport with the class at the start of the activity	3.47	VHLI
1.3.7. Learners were given enough time to finish the activity	3.45	VHLI
1.3.4. The teacher integrates PSA to the lessons	3.44	VHLI
1.3.8. Pre and post evaluation were done with assistance of the teacher	3.24	HLI
1.4. Participants' Learning	3.53	VHLI
1.4.2. Participation and cooperation to all learners were encouraged	3.61	VHLI
1.4.1. Learners were encouraged to express their ideas and feelings	3.53	VHLI
1.4.3. Learners showed interest in the activities through their participation	3.44	VHLI
1.5. Provision of Support Materials	3.25	VHLI
1.5.1. Psychosocial Activity Pack is clear and useful to the learners	3.40	VHLI
1.5.2. The teachers were provided with the Psychosocial Support Activity Pack guides and handouts.	3.20	HLI
1.5.3. The school provides materials for the learners for the Psychosocial Support Activities	3.14	HLI
1.6. Program Preparation	3.17	HLI
1.6.2. Teacher allocates a specific time for PSA within the day	3.29	VHLI
1.6.4. The venue of the activity has enough space with sanitary and hygienic conditions	3.21	HLI
1.6.3. Time allotted for every activity is enough	3.11	HLI
1.6.1. Teachers were given prior training/ orientation in conducting PSA to the learners	3.08	HLI
Overall Composite Mean	3.35	VHLI

Legend: VHLI – Very High Level of Implementation; HLI – High Level of Implementation; MLI – Moderate Level of Implementation; LLI – Low Level of Implementation

Conversely, lower ratings were noted for prior teacher training, provision of materials, and achievement of PSA objectives. Prior training for teachers is highlighted as essential for equipping them with the necessary knowledge to address mental health issues

effectively within their classrooms.

Despite the successful aspects of the PSA implementation, improvements are needed in teacher training, access to materials, and achieving program objectives. Mental health literacy training for teachers could significantly enhance their ability to identify and support students with mental health concerns, thereby increasing the effectiveness of the PSA and ensuring comprehensive support for learners. Overall, while PSA is well implemented, attention to training and resource provision is vital for sustained success.

Table 1 shows the level of implementation in the Psychosocial Support Activities (PSA) in terms of program planning and management; attainment of objectives; delivery of program content; participants' learning; provision of support materials, and program preparation.

The data revealed that "program planning and management" (3.35), "attainment of objectives" (3.36), "delivery of program content" (3.45), "participants' learning" (3.53), and "provision of support materials" (3.25) got very high level of implementation while "program preparation" (3.17) got high level of implementation. It shows that program preparation still needs improvement, however based on the overall result of PSA implementation, it earned a composite mean of 3.35 described as "very high level of implementation". This implies that Psychosocial Support Activities conducted in schools are well implemented.

It further shows that the items with high ratings are the "participation and cooperation to all learners were encouraged" (3.61), "activities were based on standard psychosocial support assessment tool" (3.53), and "PSA objectives were clearly presented" (3.50). The items with low ratings are "teachers were given prior training/ orientation in conducting PSA to the learners" (3.08), "the school provides materials for the learners for the PSA" (3.14), and "the PSA objectives were obtained" (3.14).

In order to achieve an effective implementation of the Psychosocial Support Activities, prior training is a necessity to equip the teachers with sufficient knowledge and needed materials in conducting these activities and also for the teachers to be fully aware of some mental health issues which are present in their respective classes.

It shows that PSA activities were based on standardized assessment tools. Thus, teachers were trying their best to present the objectives clearly and encourage their learners to participate and cooperate in the activities which made the implementation of the program a success. However, prior training for teachers in conducting the Psychosocial Support Activities (PSA), provision of materials, and attainment of objectives still need to be improved.

Table 2 presents the learners' psychosocial readiness in terms of psychosocial skills and psychosocial adjustment.

Table 2. *Learners' Psychosocial Readiness*

<i>Psychosocial Readiness</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
2.1. Psychosocial Skills	3.28	VHLPR
2.1.1. Teachers and classmates are ready to listen about one's ideas and feelings.	3.51	VHLPR
2.1.2. Can identify feelings like being happy, sad, angry, tired and etc.	3.47	VHLPR
2.1.7. Show strength and abilities in school.	3.36	VHLPR
2.1.6. Find ways to solve problems and trials.	3.31	VHLPR
2.1.5. Ask help from classmates, teachers, friends or family when having a hard time in learning.	3.26	VHLPR
2.1.3. Can share ideas and feelings to classmates, friends, teachers, parents and guardians.	3.20	HLPR
2.1.4. Can calm oneself when scared, angry and sad.	3.17	HLPR
2.1.8. Identify feelings or problems of classmates and others.	2.93	HLPR
2.2. Psychosocial Adjustment	3.68	VHLPR
2.2.1. Happy to be back in face-to-face class.	3.83	VHLPR
2.2.2. Like to be back in school.	3.75	VHLPR
2.2.5. Protects oneself from illness or unexpected events.	3.67	VHLPR
2.2.3. In-person class helps in learning.	3.66	VHLPR
2.2.4. Remain safe from unexpected events like calamities through safety precautions made by the school.	3.48	VHLPR
Overall Composite Mean	3.28	VHLPR

Legend: VHLPR, Very High Level of Psychosocial Readiness; HLPR, High Level of Psychosocial Readiness; MLPR, Moderate Level of Psychosocial Readiness; LLPR, Low Level of Psychosocial Readiness

Mental health literacy training for teachers can be of great help to increase the number of learners who are having mental health problems being provided with learning help and treatment supports. Based on research, the participation of teachers in mental health literacy training increases teachers' ability to determine learners with mental health problems (Woods, 2014; Langeveld et al., 2011).

The table shows the learners' psychosocial readiness, specifically psychosocial skills and psychosocial adjustment with ratings of 3.38 and 3.68 respectively, which both described as "very high level of psychosocial readiness". This shows that learners were very ready psychologically, socially and emotionally in adapting to the learning environment in school.

Moreover, "teachers and classmates are ready to listen about one's ideas and feelings" (3.51) and "happy to be back in face-to-face class" (3.83) got high ratings, while "identify feelings or problems of classmates and others" (2.93) and "remain safe from unexpected events like calamities through safety precautions made by the school" (3.48) rated the least.

It indicates that learners were very eager to attend face-to-face classes because their teachers and classmates were ready to listen to

their ideas and feelings. However, they showed less empathy in identifying feelings and problems of their classmates and some of them felt anxious being safe from unexpected events through safety precautions made by the school. This implies that learners still need psychosocial support in school for them to be more sensitive to people around them and for them to build their confidence in staying safe in school.

According to Soken-Huberty (2023), “empathy, which is the ability to understand another person’s feelings and experiences, is one of the most essential soft skills a person can have”. Starting at a young age, school is a perfect place to learn how to interact with other people, understand different perspectives, and develop good communication skills. Empathy can be taught by modeling, talking about emotions, encouraging community activities, and integrating listening activities into classwork. Through this, children are motivated to go to school because they find school as a safe place of fun experiences with good relationships with their peers.

Table 3 reflects the learners’ psychosocial well-being in terms of emotional well-being, social well-being and resilience.

Table 3. Learners’ Psychosocial Well-Being

<i>Psychosocial Well-Being</i>	<i>Weighted Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
3.1. Emotional Well-Being	2.97	HLPW
3.1.2. Felt sad.	3.11	HLPW
3.1.6. Had bad dreams.	3.11	HLPW
3.1.1. Being worried about anything.	3.04	HLPW
3.1.4. Felt helpless in a situation.	2.97	HLPW
3.1.5. Got angry or lost temper.	2.85	HLPW
3.1.3. Being bullied in school.	2.73	HLPW
3.2. Social Well-Being	3.03	HLPW
3.2.8. Felt that school is a nice place for learning.	3.43	VHLPW
3.2.5. Able to do the things he/ she wanted to during free time.	3.22	HLPW
3.2.4. Ideas were being listened and respected by parents or guidance.	3.11	HLPW
3.2.2. Spent time with friends	2.97	HLPW
3.2.7. Suggest activities or games to do with friends.	2.97	HLPW
3.2.6. Being helpful to others	2.94	HLPW
3.2.1. Being in a good mood.	2.83	HLPW
3.2.3. Understand how others feel.	2.77	HLPW
3.3. Resilience	3.05	HLPW
3.3.4. Felt that one’s ideas are listened and respected by the teacher.	3.33	VHLPW
3.3.5. Able to believe that confidence or trust helps get through hard times.	3.32	VHLPW
3.3.2. Able to understand one’s mood and feelings.	3.00	HLPW
3.3.6. Able to concentrate or pay attention to the lesson	3.00	HLPW
3.3.1. Able to calm oneself when upset or angry.	2.90	HLPW
3.3.3. Able to find friendly ways to solve misunderstandings or disputes.	2.78	HLPW
Overall Composite Mean	3.02	HLPW

Legend: VHLPW, Very High Level of Psychosocial Well-being; HLPW, High Level of Psychosocial Well-being; MLPW, Moderate Level of Psychosocial Well-being; LLPW, Low Level of Psychosocial Well-being

The data show that “emotional well-being” (2.97), “social well-being” (3.03) and “resilience” (3.05) got high level of psychosocial well-being which means that the learners’ psychosocial well-being is in a high level with an overall composite mean of 3.02. This implies that learners have a better experience in school mentally, emotionally and socially.

It further shows that “felt that school is a nice place for learning” (3.43) and “felt that one’s ideas are listened to and respected by the teacher” (3.33) got the high ratings. However, “being bullied in school” (2.73) and “understand how others feel” (2.77) got the least ratings.

This implies that learners felt that their ideas were being listened to and respected by their teachers, that is why they prefer school as the best place for learning. However, learners need to work out on their emotional well-being because some of them were affected when they experienced being bullied by their classmates. Some learners also bully their classmates maybe because they don’t understand how others feel about their actions.

Moreover, the result shows that learners have an overall positive experience in school even when they sometimes experienced being bullied as they already established self-esteem and trust to people around them which helps them in building strong social relationships in school.

Saminathen et al. (2020), concluded that school is a potential place in protecting learners against mental health problems because it supports and prepares learners socially for higher level of education and employment. However, it may also become a place of prolonged bullying and stress. Children showed interest in coming to school when they developed their emotional and social skills. They can adapt to the challenges they met in school, and this makes their learning experience fun and exciting.

Table 4 presents the significant relationship between the level of PSA implementation and psychosocial readiness, level of PSA implementation and psychosocial well-being, and psychosocial readiness and psychosocial well-being.

Table 4. Relationship among Variables Between the Level of PSA Implementation towards Psychosocial Readiness and Psychosocial Well-Being, and between the Psychosocial Readiness and Psychosocial Well-Being (N=114)

Relationship	Spearman rho	Description	P-value	Interpretation	Decision
4.1. Level of PSA Implementation and Psychosocial Readiness	0.075	Negligible Relationship	0.426	Insignificant	Accept Ho
4.2. Level of PSA Implementation and Psychosocial Well-Being	0.080	Negligible Relationship	0.397	Insignificant	Accept Ho
4.3. Psychosocial Readiness and Psychosocial Well-Being	0.399	Moderate Relationship	0.000	Significant	Failed to Accept Ho

As shown in the table, PSA Implementation in relation to psychosocial readiness and psychosocial well-being got insignificant results since it has a p-value of 0.075 and 0.080 respectively which is above 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted. This shows that there is no significant relationship between the level of PSA implementation towards learners' psychosocial readiness and learners' psychosocial well-being. This means that PSA implementation has no effect towards learners' psychosocial readiness and learners' psychosocial well-being in school. The very high and high levels of learners' psychosocial readiness and wellbeing does not affect the very high level of PSA implementation. There might be other factors affecting the learners' psychosocial readiness and well-being in school.

Moreover, psychosocial readiness and psychosocial well-being obtain a significant result since the p-value of 0.00 is less than 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the study failed to accept the null hypothesis. In other words, there is a significant relationship between the learners' psychosocial readiness and learners' psychosocial well-being. Thus, the learners' psychosocial readiness and the learners' psychosocial well-being greatly affect each other. The learners' mental, emotional and social experiences must be in a favorable state for them to be ready in adapting to the learning environment.

Studies with college students revealed that poor school adjustment is negatively related to psychological well-being. Students who have lower level of stress and have a higher level of psychological well-being, can easily adjust in school while students with poor adjustment feel difficult to manage stress and have lower levels of psychological well-being (Chui & Chan, 2020).

While the PSA's content delivery and learner participation were highly rated, the data showed a weakness in teacher training (3.08) and resource provision (3.14). These aspects are critical for program success, as well-prepared teachers can significantly influence the outcomes of psychosocial support activities. Inadequate teacher training may have limited their ability to identify and address deeper mental health concerns, which could explain the lack of significant improvements in learners' psychosocial readiness and well-being. The lower rating for the provision of materials (3.14) might have affected the quality of program delivery. Insufficient materials may have resulted in some learners not receiving the full benefits of the activities. Since access to adequate resources is necessary to facilitate effective psychosocial interventions, this gap could have reduced the overall impact of the program.

The insignificant relationship between PSA implementation and psychosocial readiness or well-being suggests that external factors beyond the program's scope may be affecting learners' mental and emotional states. Family environments, personal experiences, and community conditions may play a role in learners' psychosocial well-being, which the school-based PSA alone may not address adequately. The study did not account for these variables, which could explain the negligible relationship observed in the results.

Though the program showed a very high level of effectiveness overall (3.35), the preparation aspect received a lower score (3.17), indicating inconsistencies in how the PSA was implemented across different settings. Factors such as time allocation (3.11) and the quality of the venue (3.21) may have varied significantly, impacting how learners received and benefited from the support activities.

The importance of mental health literacy training for teachers, highlighted in the findings, suggests that the effectiveness of psychosocial interventions could improve if teachers were better equipped to recognize and manage students' mental health needs. Without this critical training, teachers may have struggled to fully implement the PSA's objectives, particularly in fostering emotional resilience and psychosocial readiness in learners.

While the program was effective in terms of participation and content delivery, learners have different emotional and psychological needs. For instance, the data on psychosocial readiness revealed that learners showed varying levels of empathy (2.93) and ability to identify others' feelings. These individual differences could have influenced how learners responded to the PSA, with some benefitting more than others, thereby weakening the overall program effect on psychosocial well-being.

While learners generally felt positive about being back in school and appreciated the supportive environment, there were still issues related to bullying (2.73) and emotional regulation (2.85), which may have diminished the overall effectiveness of the PSA. Negative school experiences, such as bullying, could counteract the positive aspects of the program, leading to insignificant changes in psychosocial well-being.

Conclusions

Psychosocial Support Activities (PSA) within school settings have shown a robust implementation, demonstrating a high level of effectiveness in supporting learners. The students participating in these programs exhibit considerable psychosocial readiness,

indicating they are prepared psychologically, socially, and emotionally to adapt to their learning environment. This readiness allows learners to engage more fully and positively in school activities.

Furthermore, children show elevated levels of psychosocial well-being, leading to improved experiences in mental, emotional, and social dimensions in the educational context. However, it is important to note that the high level of PSA implementation appears to have no direct influence on the learners' psychosocial readiness and well-being. This disconnect suggests that even though PSA is effectively implemented, other factors may play a critical role in shaping students' readiness and overall well-being.

Interestingly, there exists a significant relationship between learners' psychosocial readiness and their psychosocial well-being, indicating that these two factors influence each other significantly. Thus, while PSA programs are well-executed, the interconnectedness of readiness and well-being implies that improving one can positively impact the other. This highlights the importance of a holistic approach to mental health support in educational settings, as fostering students' psychosocial readiness can enhance their overall well-being.

It underscores the necessity for ongoing evaluation and enhancement of PSA initiatives to maximize their impact on student experiences in schools.

While the PSA implementation demonstrated a very high level of effectiveness, the results suggest that improving teacher training, resource provision, and addressing external confounding variables are essential to significantly influence learners' psychosocial readiness and well-being. The insignificant relationship observed may indicate that more comprehensive approaches are needed to address the complexity of mental health challenges in schools.

School Disaster Risk Management and Mitigation (DRMM) Coordinators are advised to incorporate Basic Psychosocial Support into their contingency plans and train teachers to assist distressed learners creatively. Schools should re-orient teachers on Psychological First Aid to prepare them for unexpected events, helping them develop strategies to address learners' fear and anxiety. This approach aims to create a safe and comfortable learning environment.

School Heads are encouraged to conduct Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions that include empathy-building activities, fostering a sense of belonging and harmonious relationships among students. Additionally, schools should reinforce their Anti-Bullying Campaigns by inviting expert speakers to raise awareness about the negative psychological and emotional impacts of bullying.

Lastly, future researchers are encouraged to conduct studies on the effectiveness of Psychosocial Support and explore other factors affecting learners' Psychosocial Readiness and Well-being, contributing to ongoing improvements in this crucial area of education.

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